

FUNCTIONS OF INTERVIEWS IN TEACHING FL

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Abstract: It is important to use various methods and techniques in teaching foreign classes according to the needs of the language learners. In this article the functions and purpose of using interview technique to improve language learners language skills are presented and given some additional recommendations.

Key words: language skills, needs analysis, interview, grammar.

Introduction

The child who fails English and bursts out crying does not need a teacher to carry on a fact-finding interview at that moment. Instead, the teacher may encourage the child to move on to an activity in which he is successful –for example, helping to plan a student - faculty play. With regard to the English test, the teacher may simple say, 'well, work this out together'. The teacher who is conducting a manipulative interview, manipulate the child into a certain frame of mind.

Methodology

Supporting, counseling, inside-giving interviews may treatment interviews. In supportive intervlews, the teacher listens, encourages, and sympathesizes. Although evident to the interviewer, the students unconscious motivations are not dealt with directly. Insight - giving interviews deal with unconscious motivations; the appropriate techniques are beyond the expertise of the most school personnel.

Questioning skills are an important part of interviewing technique. An interviewer may use several types of questions including questions that are direct, indirect, convergent, and divergent. Direct questions assume that the child knows the answer to what he is being asked.

Convergent questions require a simple, straight answer (such as yes or no)

- How old are you?
- Do you like your teacher?
- What is your favourite sport?

Divergent questions require essay - type answers: what do you think of English? Indirect question often provide information that a direct question might block. Indirect questions allow the teacher to obtain students' opinions concerning situations that may not address directly.

A leading question is one in which the answer is suggested: “You do not like English, do you?” this type of question is legitimate if it is clear what the student is

trying to answer AND THE INTERVIEWER IS MERELY PUTTING THE STUDENT'S THOUGHT INTO WORDS. However the interviewer must be careful not to put words in the child's mouth-making him say something he does not mean.

Persons often block communicating because they wish to avoid a certain topic. In such cases, the interviewer must be sensitive to painful areas and should approach cautiously from several directions. Indirect questions are useful in these situations. Another cause of communication block is one's inability to express oneself. Sometimes a neutral question, such as 'Explain what you mean', 'I don't quite understand' or 'Tell me more about it', helps to clarify meaning. It is sometimes helpful for the interviewer to apologize for not understanding. This faces some of the burden for communicating away from the child. A third cause of communication block may be the environment of the interview room. It is helpful to consider the following questions:

- What do I want the child to hear?
- Does this room enhance his learning this, or does it encourage his learning something else?
- What do I want the child to do as he enters?

So often, in an instructional setting, thought is not given to establishing rapport before getting to the purpose of the interview. The importance of establishing rapport is built into the training of school psychologists, sometimes for physicians, and not very often for classroom teachers, also we become so used to our own interview settings that we do not always think about how they look to -and affect - an interviewee. For example, the child who is anxious about English to begin with, when confronted with an array of tests or arithmetic manipulative upon entering the interview setting, may freeze.

This study set out to explore teachers' use of Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching principles and their figural creativity to see if there was a relationship with their ability to identify students' creative characteristics. It was expected that these two descriptors would have a significant relationship with the identification of their students' creative characteristics. However, these factors, Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching and teachers' figural creativity did not have a significant effect on the teachers' ability to identify students' creative characteristics. An interesting contrast to the results of the teachers' Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching findings with their identification of students' creativity characteristics was the significant relationship between the teachers' use of Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching principles and those who identified students' generic influences on learning. It suggests that the teachers are able to identify learner characteristics (generic influences) using the Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching principles as expected. In the case of this study, as shown in previous studies, teachers may lack knowledge about the creativity characteristics and therefore could not identify them. In particular,

teachers often do not identify less favorable characteristics especially those that may not be valued as creative in classroom settings (shy, ill- behaved).

The teachers' overall figural creativity scores had no significant effect on whether they identified creativity characteristics in their own students. However, patterns of creative strengths were shown to be evident among the group. For example, this group of teachers nearly all showed repeated evidence of 'breaking boundaries' in their figural drawings and almost none of them demonstrated use of humor, synthesis of figures, synthesis of lines, and emotional expressiveness.

These results lend support to the idea that one's creativity can be a function of context and teachers' conceptual understanding of creativity may be similar to those in similar environments (coworkers in this case) (Sternberg, 2000). Further, when teachers' 'creative strengths' were analyzed, richness of imagery and movement were two that had a significant relationship with teachers' ability to identify students' creative characteristics.

Another timely educational issue that this study explored was the relationship among teachers who use the Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching principles and their students' class-wide English scores. It was expected that there would be a positive relationship between teachers who use Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching principles and their students' English achievement because the Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching process is designed to alleviate English weaknesses and According to Reisman (1987), the maximize strengths (Reisman, 1987).

Conclusion

Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching process combines English content being taught with specific learner characteristics such as learning style, creativity characteristics, and generic influences on learning. For the ten subjects examined in this phase of the study, there was a positive relationship between teachers' use of Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching principles and students' English scores. The positive relationship between the two factors (Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching and Student English Scores) was expected and the low English scores that correspond to the teacher with the highest Heuristic Diagnostic Teaching use represents a class with special learning needs (academically challenged in English).

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